

ISic1225

I.Sicily inscription 1225

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea"

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140711

1. Θεοῖς Καταχθονίοις.
2. Καππαδόκων ἔθνους πολυανθέας οἶδατε ἀρούρας·
3. κεῖθεν ἐγὼ φυόμην ἐκ τοκέων ἀγαθῶν·
4. ἐξέτι τοὺς λιπόμην, δύσιν ἤλυθον ἠδὲ καὶ ἠῶ.
5. οὖνομά μοι Γλάφυρος καὶ φρενὸς εἴκελον ἦν.
6. ἐξηκοστὸν ἔτος πανελεύθερον ἐξεβίωσα
7. καὶ καλὸν τὸ τύχης καὶ πικρὸν οἶδα βίου.
- 8.

Edition: PHI334479

1. Θεοῖς Καταχθονίοις.
2. Καππαδόκων ἔθνους πολυανθέας οἶδατε ἀρούρας·
3. κεῖθεν ἐγὼ φυόμην ἐκ τοκέων ἀγαθῶν·
4. ἐξέτι τοὺς λιπόμην, δύσιν ἤλυθον ἠδὲ καὶ ἠῶ.
5. οὖνομά μοι Γλάφυρος καὶ φρενὸς εἴκελον ἦ (ν) .
6. ἐξηκοστὸν ἔτος πανελεύθερον ἐξεβίωσα
7. καὶ καλὸν τὸ τύχης καὶ πικρὸν οἶδα βίου.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492831

EDCS 39101591

PHI 140711

PHI 334479

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. *Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0400 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. *Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie.* Palermo. At 376

Libertini, G 1921. *Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche.* Florence. At 219 no.18

Ritschl, F. 1866. *Griechische Inschriften aus Sicilien. Rheinisches Museum.* 21: 137-142. At 137-138 no.1

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-22): ISic1225. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4385630>